

A brief history of orchids: discovery, lust and wealth

Nora De Angelli chronicles the whole bizarre, exotic saga of orchids

SINCE ANCIENT TIMES, they have exerted a fascination and seduction which has only increased over the centuries, sparking wonder, curiosity, admiration and passion. Orchids stand as symbols of magnificence in the world of flowering plants. A combination of their mysterious beauty, dazzling colours, strange biology, intricate shapes and hypnotizing perfumes has inspired an obsession that has lasted down the ages. The relationship between orchids and mankind is complex and encompasses discovery and adventure, witchcraft and magic, symbolism and occultism, addiction and sacrifice, lust and wealth.

The influence of China

The Chinese were the first to fully document their use of orchids which, starting almost 5,000 years ago, they used as medicinal plants. *Cymbidium* became particularly identified with Confucius (551–479 BCE), who often used orchids as an example to his students of the strength of character required to adhere to one's morals even when poor and unsupported by others.

Orchids were first collected from the wild and cultivated in the private gardens of nobles during the Wei (220–265 CE) and Chin (265–317 CE) Dynasties. In Chinese manuscripts dated 290–370 CE there are some direct references to orchids, the most common being *Cymbidium ensifolium*, *Dendrobium moniliforme* and *Vanda tessellata*.

Although orchid cultivation was common during the Song Dynasty, it became very popular during the Ming (1368–1644 CE) and Ching (1644–1911 CE) Dynasties. In the royal palaces and parks, the Chinese gardeners used to cultivate *Cymbidium* orchids in pots, and the epiphytes, such as *Vanda* and *Aerides*, suspended in baskets.

Ancient Greece

The Greek physician Hippocrates (460–377 BCE) is often called the Father of Medicine. Although he infrequently used herbal remedies, preferring to

A depiction of Confucius (below) who used orchids as a means of explaining moral self-sufficiency in his teachings.

The mysterious beauty and dazzling colours of orchids (right) have inspired fascination in people down the ages.

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treat with diet, physical therapy and rest, he did use species of Mediterranean orchids in some of his cures.

Pedanius Dioscorides (40–90 CE), a Greek physician, pharmacologist and surgeon with the Roman army, compiled the information about the many useful plants he had found on his travels into *De Materia Medica* (On Medical Materials), a 5-volume encyclopaedia. The book contained approximately 600 species of medicinal plants, »

ERNST HAECKEL (1904)

(Pictured left to right) *Cymbidium ensifolium*, *Dendrobium moniliforme* and *Vanda tessellata* were already being grown in China nearly two millennia ago.

The Doctrine of Signatures associated orchids with a perceived resemblance to the male organs of reproduction and their medicinal use was targeted accordingly.

two of which were orchids, *Orchis mascula* and *Orchis militaris*. Dioscorides also introduced the theory of the Doctrine of Signatures centred on the idea that plants could be used for medicinal purposes according to their resemblance to parts of the human anatomy. Since the tubers of *Orchis* species resembled human testicles, Dioscorides suggested that preparations of orchid tubers would heal sexually transmitted infections.

In 77 CE, Gaius Plinius Secundus, or Pliny the Elder, (23–79 CE), the Roman naturalist and philosopher, described numerous species of orchids and indicated their medicinal qualities in his treatise *Naturalis Historia* (Natural History), a synthesis of the information of that, which included also myths and folklore. Of *Orchis* roots, Pliny wrote: ‘The larger of these tuberosities, or ...the harder of the two, taken in water, is provocative of lust; while the smaller, or in other words, the softer one, taken in goat’s milk, acts as an antaphrodisiac’.

The Middle Ages and Renaissance

Contrary to the prevalent view that the medieval period was a time of darkness, the Gothic era was in fact a period of immense cultural importance, with the first universities being founded and monastic schools established. In Britain, monasteries developed herb gardens for use in the production of cures, the healing arts passed down from monks and physicians to their apprentices for generations. However, herbal concoctions began to be considered heretical meddling with the will of God and those who practiced herbalism were believed to be in league with the devil. Witches were thought to use orchid tubers in their philtres or love potions, perpetuating the belief in their aphrodisiac properties.

During the 16th century, new publications dealing with orchids became increasingly common in Europe. The Swiss-German physician, astrologer and philosopher Philippus Aureolus Theophrastus Von Hohenheim, later known as Paracelsus (1493–1541), developed the Doctrine of Signatures further in his treatise *Liber de Imaginibus* (Eternal Mind / Imagination) by describing the properties of all animals, plants and minerals and assuming associations between morphological similarities and curative properties. Much like the Ancient Romans and Greeks, he also used ground orchid tubercles from the genera *Orchis* and *Anacamptis* to make powerful aphrodisiac drinks. Of one orchid, he wrote: ‘Is it not shaped like the male privy parts? No one can deny this. Accordingly, magic discovered it and revealed that it can restore a

man’s virility and passion’.

In 1597, the English naturalist John Gerard (1545–1612) published the *General Historie of Plantes*, which became known as Gerard’s Herbal. The herbal became one of the most widely circulated English botany books of the 16th and 17th centuries. Gerard mentioned several types of *Orchis*, calling them *Satyrion feminina* or fox-stones. However, unlike many of his peers, he was of the opinion that they had little use as cures. His approach had an extensive impact on medicine in early North American colonies and species that Gerard had described were introduced to the New World from England.

Building on previous work, English botanist John Parkinson (1567–1650), apothecary to James I, published *Theatricum Botanicum* (Theater of Plants) in 1640. This was a compendium of about 3,800 plants and the largest herbal ever produced in the English language. In this he described a wide range of orchids, putting them into several different classes and separating those with oval tubers from those with palmate tubers.

First contact with the New World

After the first contact with the Bahamas by Christopher Columbus (1451–1506) in 1492, Europeans became exposed to the flora, fauna and civilizations of the New World. In the 1520s, *Vanilla planifolia* was the first New World tropical orchid to arrive in Europe, credited to the Spanish Conquistador, Hernán Cortés (1485–1547). Toward the end of the 16th century, vanilla-flavoured chocolate was being produced in Spain and had gained many admirers, including King Louis XIV of France.

During the 1600s, Europeans also began to be introduced to the flora of distant new lands discovered in Africa, the Far East and Australasia. In 1688, the first specimen of the distinctive red-flowered *Disa uniflora* was brought from South Africa. English naturalist John Ray (1627–1705) described this flower as ‘the most lovely orchid from Africa’.

The earliest Western books specifically on orchids did not appear until *Herbarium Amboinense*, a compilation written by a German-born employee of the Dutch East India Company, Georg Everhard Rumphius (1627–1702), nicknamed The Blind Seer of Ambon. *Herbarium Amboinense*, a catalogue of the plants of the island of Amboina in modern-day Indonesia, was published 39 years after his death, after severe personal tragedies had delayed publication, including the death of his wife and a daughter in an earthquake, going blind from glaucoma, loss of his library and manuscripts in »

major fire, and losing early copies of his book when the ship carrying them was sunk. Two of the 12 volumes of text were dedicated to the orchid family.

Carl Linnaeus and binomial nomenclature

The lack of a universal classification system created a lot of confusion as Europe was avalanched with new plant species. By the middle of the 18th century, the need for a shared system to classify plants became imperative. The father of modern ecology and taxonomy is Carl Linnaeus (1707–1778), a Swedish botanist, physician and zoologist. Linnaeus wrote three major works, all of which were regularly revised and updated. These were *Systema Naturae*, *Genera Plantarum* and *Species Plantarum*. These works marked the beginnings of evolutionary theory, informing the future studies of Charles Darwin and others. In *Genera Plantarum* (*The Genera of Plants* [1737]), Linnaeus first used the word *Orchidaceae* to denote the orchid family. At that time, he described only eight orchid genera, one of which was *Orchis*, a name coined by Theophrastus almost 2,000 years before.

By 1753, Carl Linnaeus had published *Species Plantarum* (*The Species of Plants*), the work that is now internationally accepted as the beginning of modern botanical nomenclature, this being the first coherent identification of plants by a genus name followed by a specific name. At the conclusion of the 18th century, classification of orchids had passed through numerous revisions, and the number of genera they had been divided into had increased. Research was assisted by the certainty botanists felt concerning which plant was being discussed in the literature.

The orchid hunters and orchidology

The search for new lands and the collection of new species of living thing attracted many botanists and adventurers. English naturalist and botanist Joseph Banks (1743–1820) and Swedish naturalist Daniel Charles Solander (1733–1782), who had trained in medicine and botany under Carl Linnaeus, sailed with James Cook on his first voyage of discovery. They brought the first three species of Australian *Dendrobium* to the attention of science in 1770. By the beginning of the 19th century, many new species of orchids had been introduced to Europe, not only from Australasia and the Pacific but also from China, the Antilles and the Americas.

Unfortunately, very few orchids survived the conditions in which the sailing ships navigated. Despite this, the stories of the sailors and explorers, as well as the specimens they brought

back, heightened interest in orchids and fired the imagination of Europeans. The hunters established a code of ruthlessness that prevails to this day. Susan Orlean, author of best-selling book *The Orchid Thief* relates, ‘If they heard that another hunter was following in their path, they would take not just every single orchid they could find, they sometimes set the place on fire. [...] There were stories of hunters urinating on each other’s shipments as they were going back to England to make sure that the plants died.’ Nevertheless, a passion developed for these exotic plants.

Sir Joseph Paxton (1803–1865), well-known English gardener, architect and Member of Parliament, became head gardener at Chatsworth House when only 20 years of age. Paxton was the first grower to build and use different greenhouses with specialized environmental conditions for cultivating orchids from different habitats. In 1820, there were just 130 species of exotic orchids grown in England, but by 1830 their number had exceeded 400. *Orchidology* was on its way.

The first reported germination of orchid seeds was of *Prescottia plantaginea*, from the Horticultural Society Garden in Chiswick, England, around 1830–1832. In 1849, the first detailed and substantiated paper on seed germination was published by David Moore (1807–1879), Director of Glasnevin Botanic Gardens, Ireland. His report in *The Gardeners’ Chronicle* was followed the same year by two additional accounts by British gardeners James Cole and Robert Gallier. But despite the intense interest and much experimentation, the secrets of orchid seed germination through mycorrhizal fungi remained a mystery.

From germination to industrial cloning

Truly major discoveries in orchid seed germination, both basic and practical, were made during the 20th century. Working in parallel with French botanist Noël Bernard, in 1904 German botanist and orchid mycorrhiza expert Hans Edmund Nicola Burgeff (1883–1976) germinated orchid seed in agar inoculated with the right species of mycorrhizal fungus. In 1922, the American biologist Lewis Knudson (1884–1958) used an improved culture medium of inorganic nutrients including copper, manganese and zinc and organic nutrients, such as sucrose, to reproduce germination in the absence of fungi. This he called the asymbiotic method. On the basis of this reasoning Knudson decided that ‘germination of orchid seeds might be obtained by the use of certain sugars’.

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Disa uniflora (above), 'the most lovely orchid from Africa', arrived in Europe in 1688.

In the 1520s *Vanilla planifolia* (left) became the first New World orchid to arrive in Europe.

Epidendrum ciliare (below) was named by Carl Linnaeus using his binomial system.

Chatsworth's Great Conservatory (above) was used to grow orchids in diverse conditions.

Seeds of *Prescottia plantaginea* (right) were the first to be germinated in cultivation.

Dendrobium discolor (below) was introduced to Europe from Australia in 1770.

JOJO MEDEROS

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Orchids in tissue culture (left), a procedure that has hugely changed the orchid trade.

Callanthe x dominyi (below left) was the first artificial orchid hybrid, made in London in 1853.

Papilionanthe Miss Joaquim (below) remains one of the most famous of all hybrid orchids.

Orchidelirium continues to thrive (bottom), though orchids in the wild have never been in greater peril.

MANUEL A. AGUILAR

RHS / SARAH CUTTLE

‘Orchidelirium is beyond addiction and beyond hope’

- William Langley

In 1949, Gavino Rotor (1917–2005) at Cornell University made the first real attempt at propagating an orchid by tissue culture. This was based on vegetative or meristematic propagation under aseptic conditions. In 1956, using Rotor's culture method, a German orchid nursery owner, Hans Thomale (1919–2002), was the first to culture stem-tip material of a European terrestrial species, *Dactylorhiza maculata*. It had taken almost 400 years from the first observation of orchid seeds to the development of a practical asymbiotic method for their germination, which did not depend on the presence of symbiotic fungi.

Orchid hybrids, an incomparable treasure

In 1849, a surgeon named John Harris (1782–1855) advised horticulturist John Dominy (1816–1891) to cross different orchid species. Dominy was employed by enlightened nursery owner, Harry James Veitch (1840–1924), proprietor of Messrs J. Veitch & Sons. By the outbreak of the First World War, the firm had introduced 1,281 plants to cultivation, among which were 232 orchid species and hybrids. In 1853, at the Veitch Nurseries establishment in Chelsea, Dominy made the first cross of different orchid species and achieved the first artificial, interspecific orchid hybrid, *Calanthe* × *dominyi*. Dominy continued to experiment with intrageneric hybrids and soon produced *Cattleya* × *hybrida*, a cross between *Cattleya guttata* and *Cattleya intermedia* which flowered in August 1859. It was shortly followed by *Cattleya* × *dominiana* (*Cattleya maxima* × *C. intermedia*), which flowered in November 1859. But probably the most widely grown of any orchid hybrid was *Calanthe* × *veitchii* (*C. rosea* × *C. vestita*), also produced in 1859.

In 1861, Dominy attempted hybridization between species belonging to different genera, *Ludisia discolor* × *Dossinia marmorata*, which generated *Dossinia dominyi*. This was the first ever artificial intergeneric orchid hybrid. From 1871, all new orchid hybrids were being published in *The Gardeners' Chronicle*, and by 1892, more than 64 new hybrids had flowered in England alone. Just one year later, one of the most popular intergeneric hybrid orchids in the world, *Papilionanthe* (*Vanda*) Miss Joaquim was disclosed to the orchid community in Singapore by its discoverer, a Singaporean Armenian horticulturist, Ashkhen Hovakimian, or Agnes Joaquim (1854–1899). At the 1899 Singapore Flower Show, *Vanda* Miss Joaquim was the main highlight, Miss Agnes had lived just long enough to see her orchid win first prize and experience public recognition for her plant. She died of cancer less

than three months later.

In 1895, the British orchid firm *Sander & Sons* began to register orchid hybrids and from 1906 it produced *Sander's Complete List of Orchid Hybrids*, a register of all orchid hybrids produced anywhere in the world. The RHS took over as International Orchid Registrar in 1961. With tens of thousands of species, orchids are the most prolific family of plants on Earth, yet humans have still found plenty of room for making more. The number of artificial hybrids is presently estimated at almost 200,000.

Orchidelirium: Past, present and future

By the beginning of the 1900s orchids had become a social symbol of luxury and wealth in the West, much as they had been in the Far East centuries before. However, after the First World War the culture of orchids in Europe recovered slowly, while in the United States and Australia it continued to expand. The culture of orchids in Europe during the Second World War was again deleteriously affected but thrived in the United States due to new technologies. A major change in focus occurred, however, which saw smaller species that were easier to cultivate in apartments used in hybridization. Orchids could at last be enjoyed by everyone.

Journalist William Langley wrote 'Orchidelirium is beyond addiction and beyond hope'. Orchids are currently grown in the largest numbers in the United States, particularly California. In Europe, the most important orchid cultivation areas are the Netherlands, Germany and France, and there is fierce competition from South East Asian countries like Thailand and Singapore where the orchid trade measures annual sales in tens of millions of dollars. The craving for new specimens has led to a massive market in illicit plants and it seems the rarer and more valuable the find the better. It cannot be known exactly how many illegally collected orchids are traded every year on the black market, though their value has been estimated at over £6 billion. The supply routes criss-cross the world and in many ways the market resembles international trade in drugs and arms.

Orchidelirium is clearly alive and well... There is little doubt that this most beautiful and intriguing member of the Plant Kingdom will remain a firm favourite, now and in the future. The only question is, will we still have wild orchids growing in their natural habitats, or only under artificial conditions? Time will tell. ○

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